

Opportunities, Status and Challenges Faced by Women Entrepreneurs in India

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Gomathi, C & Priyadeepa, S. "Opportunities, Status and Challenges Faced by Women Entrepreneurs in India." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 194–200.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1461484>

Dr.C.Gomathi, M.Com.,M.Phil.,B.Ed.,Ph.D.,

Assistant Professor PG & Research Department of Commerce

Mrs.S.Priyadeepa, M.Com (CA),M.Phil.(Ph.D.),

Research Scholar, Sri Vidya Mandir Arts and Science College, Katteri, Uthangarai

Abstract

Entrepreneurship refers to the act of setting up a new business to take advantages of new opportunities. Entrepreneurs are responsible for shaping the economy and they help in the creation of new wealth and new jobs by inventing new products, process and services. The purpose of the paper to examine the constraints and opportunities facing female entrepreneurship in developing countries at the micro- and macro-level perspectives and seeks to provide a detailed account of the opportunities and constraints brought by entrepreneurship. Another main purpose of this paper is to analyze the present status and policies of Indian government for women and also to analyse that are those policies adequate for the growth and opportunities of Women entrepreneurship. This paper includes rationale grounds behind the women entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, women, economy, economic development, challenges, economic growth, remedial measures, opportunities of women entrepreneurship.

Introduction

“The best thermometer to the progress of a nation is its treatment of its women.”- Swami Vivekananda.

In Hindu scriptures, the woman is described as the epithet of Shakti which means the source of power. By the using of the Shakti, a woman can do anything. In the 21st century, the business women in the form of women entrepreneurs are highest rising entrepreneurial populations in India. Women’s entrepreneurship needs to be studied separately for two main reasons. The first reason is that women’s entrepreneurship has been recognized during the last decade as an important untapped source of economic growth. Women entrepreneurs create new jobs for themselves and others and by being different also provide society with different solutions to management, organization and business problems as well as to the exploitation of entrepreneurial opportunities. Now a day educated women do not want to limit their lives in the four walls of the house. They demand equal respect from their partners. However, Indian women have to go a long way to achieve equal rights and position because traditions are deep rooted in Indian society where the sociological set up has been a male-dominated one. However, they

still represent a minority of all entrepreneurs. Thus, a woman entrepreneur is one who starts the business and manages it independently and tactfully, takes all the risks, faces the challenges boldly with an iron will to succeed.

According to MedhaDubhashiVinze, a woman entrepreneur is a person who is an enterprising individual with an eye for opportunities and an uncanny vision, commercial acumen, with tremendous perseverance and above all a person who is willing to take risks with the unknown because of the adventurous spirit she possesses.

According to J. Schumpeter “Women who innovate initiate or adopt business actively are called women entrepreneurs.”

According to APJ Abdul Kalam, “Empowerment of women is essential as their thoughts and their value systems lead to the development of a good family, good society and ultimately a good nation.”

Objectives of the Study

- To discuss the role and status of women entrepreneurs.
- To discuss the challenges and opportunities of women entrepreneurs.
- To discuss the obstacles faced by women entrepreneurs.
- To discuss the major factors affecting the development of women entrepreneurship.
- To discuss the measures needed to improve the state of women entrepreneurship.
- To discuss some successful leading business women.

Review of Literature

The focus of the literature review will be on the concept of entrepreneurship and then drive on to look at female entrepreneurship and related definitions. An important tool considered in allowing female empowerment and liberation is Female Entrepreneurship.

Bowen&Hisrich, (1986), evaluated many research studies done on women entrepreneurship. It concluded that female entrepreneurs are relatively well educated in general but are not having proper management skills, high in internal locus of control than other women in their values & are likely to have had entrepreneurial fathers.

Dzisi (2008: 3–4) defines entrepreneurship from the economic point of view, quoting the definition given by Schumpeter and Krizner. “Schumpeter (1934) described the entrepreneur as the innovator who introduces something new into an economy” and “Krizner (1997 – authors’ own addition) stressed the fact that the entrepreneur is the decision maker in a particular cultural context, who commands a range of behaviors that exploit these opportunities.”

Cohoon, Wadhwa& Mitchell, (2010), present a detail about men & women entrepreneur’s background and experiences. The study is based on the data collected from primary data where surveys were conducted to collect data from established & successful women entrepreneurs.

Role of Women Entrepreneurs

Entrepreneurship is not a male prerogative. It’s been evidenced that women entrepreneurship has gained momentum in the last three decades with the increase in the number of women enterprises and their substantive contribution to the economic growth in the country. Women enter entrepreneurship due to economic factors which pushed them to be on their own and urge them to do something independently. We see a lot of women professionals in engineering, medicine, law, etc. They are also setting up hospitals, training centers, etc.

Present Status of Women Entrepreneur

Present Position of Women Entrepreneurs in India Women represents approximately half of the total world population as well as in India also. Women are the better half of the society. In our societies, Indian women are treated as show pieces to be kept at home. But now they are also enjoying the impact of globalization not only on domestic but also on the international sphere. Women come out of the four walls to contribute to all activities. Indian women are ready to take the burden of work in-house and as well as the workplace. From many surveys, it is discovered that the female entrepreneurs from India are producing more capitals than the other part of the world. Since mid-1991, a drastic change takes place in the Indian Economy. India has great entrepreneurial potential. At the present era, women participation in financial activities is marked by a low work participation rate. India provides a good example of women entrepreneurship.

Opportunities for Women Entrepreneurs

Education is a boon to mankind, while lack of education to a person is a bane nowadays. The emergence as well as the development of women entrepreneurs is quite visible in India and their overall contribution to the Indian economy is also very significant. Today the role of Women entrepreneur in economic development is inevitable because women are entering not only in selected professions but also in professions like trade, industry and engineering. Women should be considered as the specific target group for all development programmes. In recent days women, entrepreneurs are performing various activities.

- Tourism industry
- Telecommunication
- Plastic materials
- Mineral water
- Sericulture
- Floriculture
- Herbal & health care

Challenges for Women Entrepreneur

Not Being Taken Seriously

Within the business world, women's opinions and advice are not always viewed as "expert" compared to a man's opinion. And when a female starts a business, sometimes family, friends, and others in the business community can view it as a hobby or a side project to family duties, rather than a bona fide business. Seeking out extra support can help to help overcome this bias, but women need to realize that this is a true gender bias obstacle.

Letting Fear Stand in the Way

In general, women can be less prone to taking risks and can let their fears (such as the fear of failure, fear of success, fear of being on their own, etc.) stand in the way of "going for it" and pursuing the path of entrepreneurship. Confidence is a great way to combat these fears and the best way to feel confident in what you are doing is to make sure that you are as prepared as possible before you start your business endeavor. Also, believe in what you bring to the table and value your time, efforts and capabilities.

Wanting to Please Everyone

Females are often taught to "be nice" and "people pleasers," which can lead to seeking the approval of others. Subsequently, women can have a harder time saying "No," which can lead to

under-charging for their products/services or being too giving of their time and help in general. This typically comes at the expense of their own needs, business or otherwise.

Wearing Too Many Hats

In their personal lives, women tend to try to be everything to everyone and wear so many different hats that juggling everything becomes very difficult. So, when women add “entrepreneur” and “business owner” into the mix, this tendency is further magnified. Women can feel like they have to “do it for themselves” or are the best person for every job and have a tougher time delegating responsibilities to others. This causes more time to be spent working in their business, rather than on their business. This is a major hurdle to overcome to have a successful business.

Not Being Able to “Toot Your Own Horn”

Being able to speak about your accomplishments honestly and with pride is a necessity for a successful business owner or entrepreneur. Sometimes, women feel uncomfortable talking about their achievements and may feel like they are bragging or being too boastful. But your achievements and accomplishments are some of the biggest selling points your business has, so don’t be afraid to put them out there! Overcoming these five challenges will help put you on a path toward a more successful business.

Obstacles Faced by Women Entrepreneurs

Highly educated, talented and professionally qualified women should be encouraged for running their own business, rather than reliant on wage service jobs. They are faced with many problems to get ahead their life in business. A few problems can be detailed:

Family Restriction: Women are expected to spend more time with their family members. They do not encourage women to travel extensively for exploiting business opportunities.

The Problem of Finance: Finance is regarded as “life-blood” for any enterprise, be it big or small. However, women entrepreneurs suffer from the shortage of finance on two counts. Firstly, women do not generally have property in their names to use them as collateral for obtaining funds from external sources. Thus, their access to the external sources of funds is limited.

Lack of Education: Women are generally denied higher education, especially in rural areas and under developed countries. Women are not allowed to enrich their knowledge in technical and research areas to introduce new products.

Role Conflict: Marriage and family life are given more importance than career and social life in Indian society.

Unfavorable Environment: The society is dominated by males. Many business men are not interested to have the business relationship with women entrepreneurs. Male generally do not encourage women entrepreneurs.

Lack of Persistent Nature: Women generally have sympathy for others. They are very emotional. This nature should not allow them to get easily cheated in business.

Lack of Mental Strength: Business involves risk. Women entrepreneurs get upset very easily when the loss arises in business.

Lack of Information: Women entrepreneurs are not generally aware of the subsidies and incentives available for them. Lack of knowledge may prevent them from availing the special schemes.

Stiff Competition: Women face a lot of competition from men. Due to limited mobility, they find difficult to compete with men.

Mobility: Moving in and around the market, is again a tough job for Middle-Class Women Entrepreneurs in the Indian social system.

Remedial Measures

Some of the remedial measures that can be undertaken to promote women entrepreneurship in India are as follows.

Promotional Help: Government and NGOs must assist entrepreneurs, both in financial and non-financial areas.

Training: Women entrepreneurs must be given the training to operate and run a business successfully. Training has to be given to women who are still reluctant to take up the entrepreneurial task.

Selection of Machinery and Technology: Women require assistance in selection of machinery and technology. Assistance must be provided to them in technical areas so that the business unit become successful.

Finance: Finance is one of the major problems faced by women entrepreneurs. Both family and government organizations should be liberal in providing financial assistance to them.

Marketing Assistance: Due to limited mobility, women are unable to market their goods. Assistance must be provided to help them to market their goods successfully in the economic environment.

Family Support: Family should support women entrepreneurs and encourage them to establish and run the business successfully.

Insights about Women's Entrepreneurship Development

The following are the facts and insights about Women's Entrepreneurship Development:-

- Entrepreneurship Development Programmes (EDPs) to cater to the needs of potential women entrepreneurs, who may not have adequate educational background and skills are being steered by the Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) development organizations.
- SIDBI has been implementing two special schemes for women
- Mahila Udyam Nidhi which is an exclusive scheme for providing equity to women entrepreneurs.
- Mahila Vikas Nidhi which offers developmental assistance for pursuit of income generating activities to women.
- Loan facility for the small business sector under the Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana.
- The Sakha Fund is a private venture fund that promotes woman participation in entrepreneurship.
- Stand-Up India Scheme facilitates bank loans to Women entrepreneur.
- Under Annapurna Scheme Government of India helps those women who are into the business of food catering.
- Trade Related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development (TREAD) under the ministry of MSME to promote women entrepreneurs.

Measures to Improve Women Entrepreneurship

Women entrepreneurship faces many challenges and requires in the development of society and also entrepreneurial activities. Adequate training programmed on management skills to be provided to women community. To encourage the women's participation in decision-making. Counseling through the help of committed NGOs, managerial experts and technical personnel should be provided to existing and emerging women entrepreneurs for developing the business activities. Continuous monitoring should be the need for the improvement of training programmers. The main activities for women are trained should focus on their marketability, profitability. The leadership qualities must be needed to improve and extend their women entrepreneurs. Setting up a good infrastructure is also required to build entrepreneurship opportunities.

Some Successful Leading Business Women Entrepreneur in India

- Akhila Srinivasan, Managing Director, Shriram Investments Ltd
- Chanda Kochhar, Executive Director, ICICI Bank
- Chitra Ramakrishnan, MD & CEO, National Stock Exchange
- Ranjana Kumar, Chairman, NABARD
- Mallika Srinivasan, Chairman & CEO, TAFE Ltd
- Neelam Dhawan, Managing director of Microsoft India
- Renuka Ramnath, CEO, ICICI Ventures
- Ritu Kumar, Fashion Designer
- Shahnaz Hussain, CEO, Shahnaz Herbals

Suggestions

To resolve the above problems faced by the women entrepreneurs the following suggestions are recommended.

- Financial Aspects: Special schemes should be implemented whereby women can get bank loans at decent conditions.
- Working time: Self-employed women should be encouraged to employ on a part-time or full-time basis at least one person so that they have more time for their family and can take an interest in other occupations, actively participate in decision-making bodies.
- Training, advice or consultancy targeted solely or mainly at women entrepreneurs
- Start-up programmes for women, particularly those returning to the labor market.
- Special targeting of women in general campaigns to boost levels of entrepreneurship.
- Equal opportunities policies are aiming for equal access for women to services.
- Most of the women entrepreneurs are started their business under sole proprietorship & small scale. So that government has to aid their business and help those to start the large-scale business like company form of organization.
- Most of the Women Entrepreneurs are getting their finance from banking and Financial Institutions. So that government has to take the initiative and supportive role for both banks and women entrepreneurs.
- The government has to conduct special training programs, entrepreneurial development programmes, and improvement programs for Women Entrepreneurs as well as their employees to enhance their productivity.
- Women entrepreneurs and women employees have to play dual roles as a family organizer and manager of the women enterprise. So that government has to preview the extension of labor laws and benefits to their organizations

Conclusion

“When women move forward, the family moves, the village moves, and the nation move” these words of Pandit Jawaharlal Lal Nehru are an accepted fact. Nowadays women enter not only in selected professions but also in the profession like trade, industry, and engineering. Women entrepreneurs need to be given assurance, freedom, and mobility to come out of their absurdities. The following actions are recommended to authorize the women to grab different opportunities and face challenges in their business. (i) Awareness program must be conducted on a huge scale for increasing awareness among women, (ii) There must be a constant attempt to inspire, motivate women entrepreneurs, (iii) By arranging unlimited vocational training to women community to understand them the production process and production management, (iv) Proper training programs must be organized to develop professional competencies in managerial, leadership, financial,

production process, profit planning, marketing, maintaining books of accounts and other skills. These all will encourage women to start the business, (v) Educational institution should tie up with various government and non-government agencies to support in entrepreneurship development, (vi) Various schemes plans must be provided by the government to develop entrepreneurs in the state. E.g. the Prime ministers RozgarYojana, Community Development Programme (CDP), Scheme of Discriminatory Interest Rate, Rural village industries scheme etc, (vii) The financial institutions should lend their hand to provide more working capital assistance both for small-scale venture and large-scale ventures, (viii) NGOs and government organizations must spread information about policies, plans and strategies on the improvement of women in the field of industry, trade and commerce. Women entrepreneurs should employ the various schemes provided by the Government, (ix) Workshops and seminars should be organized frequently for women entrepreneurs to make their relations more cordial. (x) The government should recognize the successful or growing women entrepreneurs and award them.

References

- Baporikar, N. (2007). Entrepreneurship development & project management- Himalaya publication house.
- Dhameja, K —Women Entrepreneurs: Opportunities, Performance, Problems Deep Publications Pvt., Ltd., New Delhi, P – 9.
- Gordon, E. & Natarajan K. (2007). Entrepreneurship development – Himalaya publication house, second revised edition.
- Rani, D. L. (1996). Women Entrepreneurs, New Delhi, APH Publishing House.
- Singh, Bharat (2016). “Women Entrepreneurship in India: Role of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises” in “Women Entrepreneurship in India-Potential and Prospects.” Kunal Books, New Delhi.

Web Sources

- <http://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/UploadFolder/ENTREPRENEURS.pdf>
- [http://iosrjournals.org/iosr-jbm/pages/20\(5\)Version-8.html](http://iosrjournals.org/iosr-jbm/pages/20(5)Version-8.html)
- http://www.iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/uploadfolder/IJCIET_09_04_012/IJCIET_09_04_012.pdf
- <http://www.ijsrp.org/research-paper-1117/ijsrp-p7122.pdf>
- <http://www.internationaljournalssrg.org/IJEMS/2016/Volume3-Issue5/IJEMS-V3I5P120.pdf>
- <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jbm/papers/Vol17-issue8/Version-3/I017836973.pdf>
- <http://www.oecd.org/cfe/smes/31919215.pdf>
- <http://www.rroij.com/open-access/women-entrepreneurs--problems-of-womenentrepreneurs-.php?aid=48589>
- <https://accountlearning.com/challenges-problems-faced-women-entrepreneurs-remedial-measures/>
- https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/978-0-85729-320-6_43.pdf
- <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/a839/9756d4faf59373852a9b905b1159947a93e3.pdf>
- <https://www.carolroth.com/blog/entrepreneurship-5-challenges-facing-women-entrepreneurs/>
- https://www.ripublication.com/gjfm-spl/gjfmv6n9_25.pdf
- <https://www.studymode.com/essays/Women-Entrepreneurs-In-India-1663254.html>